

**RESHAPING EUROPEAN ADVANCES TOWARDS GREEN LEADERSHIP
THROUGH DELIBERATIVE APPROACHES AND LEARNING**

**D3.1 Issues and topics selected for empirical
investigations and implementations in
13 EU-countries and for deliberative formats
at EU-level based on an agreement with the
Funding Authority**

**WP3 – Testing and validating innovative deliberative formats
and tools**

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Project Summary

REAL DEAL will stimulate a pan-European debate to reshape citizens' and stakeholders' active participation through deliberative processes around the European Green Deal (EGD). It brings together researchers and practitioners of deliberative democracy from a wide range of disciplines including environmental rights and the law of public participation, ethics and responsible innovation, gender studies and ecofeminism, psychology, geography, urban planning, and sustainability studies. It includes the EU's largest civil society networks advocating on the environment, climate, sustainable development, local democracy, and the European movement. It teams up with youth climate, social justice and women's organisations, SMEs, universities and research institutes, mobilising networks with thousands of CSOs, uniting millions of citizens and activating contacts to thousands of policymakers. In a large co-creation exercise, REAL DEAL will develop, test, and validate innovative tools and formats to propel deliberative democracy to the next level. It will test its innovations at citizens assemblies for the transition in at least 13 countries. We will scrutinise pan-European formats ranging from digital deliberation through our online platform www.realdeal.eu to in-person processes such as an Assembly for a Gender-Just Green Deal and a pan-European Youth Climate Assembly. REAL DEAL will co-create a comprehensive protocol for meaningful citizens' participation and deliberation to work towards the objectives of the EGD. It will validate recommendations on how to design such processes and how they can be applied by European institutions, Member States, and civil society alike. Gender equality will be embedded into the project's DNA. It pays specific attention to the leave-no-one-behind principle, fostering the engagement of disenfranchised groups that are disproportionately burdened by environmental damage. REAL DEAL will develop a new model of environmental citizenship across Europe.

Project Information

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Website	www.realdeal.eu

Consortium partners

Logo	Partner	Abbreviation	Country
	INSTITUTE FOR ADVANCED SUSTAINABILITY STUDIES	IASS	Germany
	EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL BUREAU	EEB	Belgium
	ALLEANZA ITALIANA PER LO SVILUPPO SOSTENIBILE	ASviS	Italy
	ASSOCIATION DES AGENCES DE LA DEMOCRATIE LOCALE	AADL/ALDA	France
	CENTRAL EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY	CEU	Hungary
	CLIMATE ACTION NETWORK EUROPE	CAN EUROPE	Belgium
	DIALOGIK	DIA	Germany
	EUROPEAN MOVEMENT INTERNATIONAL	EMI	Belgium
	GLOBAL CLIMATE FORUM	GCF	Germany
	FORENINGEN NYT EUROPA	NYT EUROPA	Denmark
	SOLIDAR	SOLIDAR	Belgium
	TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF BERLIN	TUB	Germany
	TRILATERAL RESEARCH	TRI IE	Ireland
	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY & RESEARCH	WR	Netherlands
	WOMEN ENGAGE FOR A COMMON FUTURE	WECF	Germany
	YOUTH AND ENVIRONMENT EUROPE	YEE	Czech Republic

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Executive summary

The present report documents the result of task 3.1, whose goal was to select specific issues and topics for the experimental deliberative activities. It presents the arguments and procedural steps that have led to the selection of three topics to be used as focus of the deliberative formats that we will develop and test in WP3 of the REAL DEAL project. The topics are: mobility, food and health, and financing the European Green Deal. They will be combined with cross cutting issues, namely gender equality, the leave-no-one-behind principle, and the future of democracy in the face of global change. A list of more than 25 items for discussion will be used to tailor topics and issues in view of the situation of different countries. These topics, issues, and items resulted first from scientific arguments, second from exchanges in the consortium, and finally from extremely fruitful dialogues with EU officials to whom we want to express our gratitude.

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List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
EU	European Union
REAL DEAL	RESHAPING EUROPEAN ADVANCES TOWARDS GREEN LEADERSHIP THROUGH DELIBERATIVE APPROACHES AND LEARNING
EGD	European Green Deal
GDSO	Green Deal Support Office
WP	Work package

Table 1 List of acronyms/abbreviations

Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
Topic	A focus for deliberation to be used in about four member states
Issue	A cross-cutting theme that will be integrated in deliberations in all countries with all topics
Item	A specific element that can help to tailor topics and issues to particular countries

Table 2 Glossary of terms

1. Introduction

When unveiling the European Green Deal in December 2019, Ursula von der Leyen, president of the Commission, characterized it as follows: „The European Green Deal is, on the one hand, our vision for a climate-neutral continent in 2050, and on the other hand a very dedicated roadmap whose goal is 50 actions for 2050” (Hutchinson, 2019). Implementing such an ambitious and complex agenda in a union with a total population of nearly half a billion, distributed over 27 countries, each of which holds regular national elections, requires new levels of deliberative democracy and citizens participation. This is all the more important because democracy is not a state of perfection realized once and for all, but a regulative idea highlighting rooms for improvement in the current state of political systems.

The REAL DEAL project will develop and validate the innovative formats of deliberative democracy needed for this purpose, testing them in at least 11 EU member states. We will also test them in a combination of two additional countries with a fixed topic, reaching a total of 13. Whether the original idea of performing such tests in Ukraine will be feasible in the duration of the project remains to be seen. The first step in this process, and the objective of Task 3.1, is the identification of topics and issues to be discussed in these tests, as documented in this report. In the present context, a *topic* is the focus of deliberation (an example might be the use of biomass in order to reduce carbon emissions from power plants). Given the limited resources, in each country, one topic shall be addressed (exceptions may be feasible). To ensure comparability, each one of the three topic shall be addressed in at least three countries. In the present context, an *issue* is a theme that can and shall be integrated into the deliberation of any topic selected (an example might be citizens’ and stakeholders’ trust in the commission and other European institutions). This provides the basis for Task 3.4 and its sub-tasks, where the topics, issues, and items will be used to test the validity of different participative formats in different countries across the EU.

The present report documents the arguments that have led to the final selection of topics and issues as well as the steps performed in the selection process.

2. First step: scientific arguments

2.1 Decarbonisation focused topic

Because realising a climate-neutral EU by 2050 is the primary – but by no means only – goal of the European Green Deal, one might consider as salient those topics that are particularly important for EU-wide decarbonisation while requiring exceptional political effort.

Figure 1 shows that most sectors – energy supply, industry, etc. – have achieved significant reductions in the past decades. Accelerating these reductions towards carbon neutrality in 2050 will be hard, but not impossible. Emissions from transport and Biomass use, however, have increased, with transport being the bigger emitter of the two.

For a topic to be suitable for the present purpose, the environmental impact is important, but not sufficient. On top of it, the relevance for European citizens is essential, too. In the case of

transport, this relevance has been ascertained in at least two dimensions. First, air pollution, noise, and accidents caused by present mobility patterns are a key concern for many citizens, especially in urban settings. The list can be expanded: social costs of commuting, lack of accessibilities to basic infrastructure and services, problems with inequality, and the existence of segregated cities/spaces in Europe matter as well.

Second, Boyer et al. (2020) have shown that measures making individual mobility more expensive and sometimes cumbersome can be a trigger for massive social protests, especially in rural settings. These arguments speak in favor of selecting “MOBILITY” (with a focus on individual mobility in urban and rural regions) as one of the three topics to be used as focus in the formats for deliberative democracy that REAL DEAL will develop and test.

Figure 1 - EU Greenhouse gas emissions by sector, 1990-2018
Source: EEA, 2019

Before moving to other possible topics, it is important to consider scientific arguments relating to cross-cutting issues that will play a role in all topics and countries. These issues arise because the European Green Deal is about more than climate neutrality (Wolf et al., 2021), as Frans Timmermans emphasized from the very beginning when he said, “The European Green Deal is an opportunity to improve the health and well-being of our people by transforming our economic model” (Hutchinson, 2019). This requires considering the intersectionality between the many forms of discrimination and inequality that still characterize the EU as well as world society (Runyan, 2018). They matter because the impacts of climate change hit disadvantaged people more than others, while emissions causing climate change are produced to a considerable extent by the privileged ones. Discrimination and inequality matter even more because they undermine the solidarity that is necessary to improve, in Timmermans’ words, the health and well-being of our people. Therefore, gender equality as well as the leave-no-one-behind principle are key cross-cutting issues for all deliberative formats that will be tested by REAL DEAL. Given the purpose of the REAL DEAL project, another cross-cutting issue will obviously be the future of democracy in the face of global change.

2.2 People focused topic

The most recent comprehensive data about how people in the European Union prioritise issues in their respective countries are summarised in figure 2. In the survey, people were asked to identify the two most important issues facing their country. Health was seen by 28% of people in the European Union as being one of the two most important issues facing their country. There is little doubt that the Covid pandemic was a key reason for this result, but rapidly increasing research about the relationship between health and happiness is showing how important this relation is for people (Steptoe, 2019).

Figure 2 - Most important national issues in the European Union 2021
Source: Statista, 2022

In view of the European Green Deal, it is important to notice that only 18% mentioned the environment as one of the two most important issues, and barely 4% mentioned energy supply. The top positions after health are taken by the economy (26%), inflation (23%) and unemployment (21%). We will come back to the importance of economic issues in the next subsection. Here we focus on the triangular relation between health, environment, and happiness, because in everyday life environmental concern – which is central for the European Green Deal – is intimately connected to daily diets and their connection with health and happiness (Moore Lappé, 1981). Research on the relation between environment and happiness is highlighting the many connections between them (Helliwell et al., 2020). Concepts of planetary health and one health (Yasobant and Saxena, 2019) emphasize the connections between human health and the state of the environment. In the everyday life of European citizens, the nexus between health, environment and happiness is salient in their daily diets.

At the same time, considering the supply chains for food in the European Union raises far reaching questions about agriculture, biodiversity and land use, as the expansion of the European Green Deal from the initial emphasis on decarbonisation to these transformative

areas shows. These arguments speak in favor of defining health, food, agriculture and biodiversity as a second focal topic – “FOOD AND HEALTH” for short. Given the special importance of food safety for mothers and the large role of women in buying and preparing food the issue of gender equality will be an integral part of deliberations about this topic. Last not least, as shown in figure 1, greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture and biomass use are significant challenges for the decarbonisation dimension of the European Green Deal, too.

2.3 Economy focused topic

Figure 2 shows that in the view of European citizens economic issues deserve a high priority – an understandable position given the experiences of the 2007-2008 global financial crisis, the subsequent 2009-2010 Euro-crisis, and the Covid-related 2020 global recession. In the meantime, the impact of the Ukraine war reinforces economic worries among citizens as well as among experts and decision-makers.

When unveiling the European Green Deal, von der Leyen addressed these concerns by saying that “The European Green Deal is on the one hand about cutting emissions, but on the other hand about creating jobs and boosting innovation.” She also mentioned that this would imply significant additional annual investment, estimated by the EU Commission to be in the order of €260bn. In the meantime, slowing real growth, accelerating inflation and declining real wages (Schnabel, 2029) have intensified the challenge. Add to this the growing economic and technological competition from the US and China the EU is faced with, and it becomes understandable that financing the European Green Deal is a huge challenge.

From the point of view of most European citizens this raises fundamental questions about European solidarity. At the time of writing, there is broad agreement that key financial rules (in particular about state aid) should be relaxed because they hamper attempts to create ecosystems of companies that will be able to face their competitors in the U.S. and China. But many member states fear that France and Germany want to form national champions, leaving the rest of Europe out (Suanzes, 2023). Mistrust that goes back to the Euro-crisis puts the European Green Deal at risk. Civil society can and should heal wounds here, and REAL DEAL presents the opportunity to investigate the thorny issue of financing the European Green Deal in a perspective of European solidarity. These arguments speak in favor of choosing the financing of the European Green Deal, EU GREEN FINANCE as the third topic to be used as focus in the formats for deliberative democracy to be developed and tested. Along these lines, REAL-DEAL can realize the commitment – expressed in the grant agreement – to stimulate a pan-European debate to reshape citizens’ and stakeholders’ active participation through deliberative processes around the European Green Deal.

3. Second step: Items suggested by consortium partners

The partners of the REAL DEAL consortium collected a variety of items for deliberation that might be used in formats of deliberative democracy relating to the European Green Deal. This started at the kick-off meeting of WP3, was continued in an email survey, a first round with little response, then after reminders with suggestions from nearly all partners. Table 3 gives an overview of the results. The idea was and is not to introduce each one of these

items explicitly as input to the deliberative events organised by REAL DEAL, but to observe whether the participants drive the discussion in directions suggested by the items.

In the top row of the table the first three columns correspond to the topics, the next two to the cross-cutting issues introduced in section 2. The last column assembles heterogeneous items that, without ignoring their importance and interest, could not be grouped in a coherent topic or issue. The empirical work of REAL DEAL will include checking whether and if so when these items will surface in the actual deliberations.

Table 3 Items for deliberation suggested by REAL DEAL partners.

Mobility	Food and Health	Green EU Finance	Future of Democracy	Fairness	Not assigned
Movements towards accessible, cheaper transport		De-industrialisation in EU	Mock climate negotiations in school	Energy poverty measures	
Use of public spaces	Ecosystem services and biodiversity	Views on the Green Agenda for the Western Balkans and the IPA III fund	Women who not usually vote: set the agenda for what changes they would want to see	Energy responses (winter 22/23)	Universal income
Redirect use of streets	Conflict over natural resources	Financing circular economy	Efforts towards tools for deliberative democracy	Promoting energy efficient renovation within households of marginalised communities	"Educational ecosystem"
Urban mobility (see above, it is the same item)	Agriculture: stop funding harmful intensive farming practices	Well-being economy (beyond GDP)	Politicisation of key topics	Adressing marginalised communities	The role of science
Transition to bioeconomy/alternative futures- what is the relation with mobility?		Investments outside and inside the EU	Lack of willingness public institutions to integrate the outcomes of participatory processes within national/regional strategic planning and operational plans	Energy price explosion	Trust in science – connected to the future of democracy
Clean air/ zero pollution action plan implemented at national and local levels		Application of strong sustainability in economic models (see taxonomy for the financing of sustainable activities)	The feeling of disaffection toward politics and of democratic deficit among the citizens	Consumer price inflation, cost of living	
			The promoters of the participative processes are not able to create a "critical mass"	Equitable access to integrated well-being and health services	
			Reproductive justice	Social deprivation - climate of 2nd order importance	
			Feeling of lack of power of the people	Access to a clean, healthy and sustainable environment as universal human right (UN)	
			Faith in politicians	Green data 4 all	

			The rule of law and public participation in Europe		
			How to strengthen democracy – promote social innovation?		

When analysing the data from different deliberative formats and different countries, these items will be used as a grid to identify on the one hand how far the sense of priorities in the REAL DEAL consortium differs from the perspective expressed by the citizens and stakeholders involved, on the other hand how far these perspectives depend on the format and country.

4. Third step: Dialogue with EU representatives

An essential element in the process of designing and selecting topics, issues, and items was the non-public Dialogue on Selected European Green Deal Policy Priorities organized by GDSO on January 12th. There, 16 EU-officials presented European Green Deal policy priorities for the year ahead and discussed them with the projects in the Green Deal Call. This helped us to define topics, issues and items in such a way as to create opportunities for important synergies across the spectrum of relevant projects, each of which with its own characteristics.

The areas covered in this dialogue were Public Participation / Climate action / Biodiversity / Clean, affordable and secure energy / Food / Health / Urban environment / Mobility. Given the time horizon envisaged by the REAL DEAL project a limitation on a single year would be misplaced, and for ensuring comparability with the limited resources available eight topics would be inappropriate. However, the policy priorities discussed at the event helped us to crystallize the three topics identified in section 2 on the basis of scientific arguments: mobility was already on the list, and it clearly relates to urban environment, too. The health-food nexus emerged out of this event along with the connection with biodiversity. The latter connection was not discussed at the event for the obvious reason that agriculture, despite its massive importance for EU policy making, was not on the agenda of this particular event (it was, however, an important theme of discussion in the workshop performed by Task 1.4). Financing the European Green Deal was not on the agenda either, while nobody would think that therefore it is not important.

To clarify how best to deal with the topics developed in section 2 based on the science related to the EU Green Deal, a direct conversation took place, involving the main authors of this report together with a representative of IASS as project coordinator of REAL DEAL, and two officials of the EU, namely Wilhelmus de Wilt of DG Environment, unit C3 Clean air, and Rikke Karlsson of the DG for Health and Food Safety. When preparing this conversation, we emailed 20 EU officials asking them whether they would be available for subsequent exchanges via email or phone. Those who sent a positive response will be precious points of reference in the design and implementation of the deliberative events envisaged by REAL DEAL.

The conversation with Mr. de Wilt and Ms. Karlsson helped us first of all to realise to what extent by now the European Green Deal is developing as an opportunity – in Frans Timmermans' words quoted above – to improve the health and well-being of our people by transforming our economic model. Next, that conversation led us to crystallise the topic of food and health by looking deeper into the connections between food, agriculture, biodiversity, health and happiness. Last not least, the forceful arguments advanced by our interlocutors (and picked up by us in subsection 2.3 above) convinced us that it would be a grave mistake to drop the topic of how to finance the European Green Deal.

5. Conclusion

Against the background of global climate change, financial crises, the Covid pandemic, and most recently the war in Ukraine it is understandable that many people tend to imagine the future as gloomy if not disastrous. As a fascinating alternative the European Green Deal (EGD) offers a vision for vigorous collective action at the scale of the European continent. To effectively realize such action will require new forms of resonance (Rosa, 2019) between the institutions of the European Union and its citizens. REAL DEAL will develop and test formats of deliberation that can foster such resonance.

For that purpose, the core aim of the European Green Deal, i.e. climate neutrality by 2050, can be discussed by using the topic of mobility – in urban and rural contexts – as focus of deliberation. But the EGD is about more than climate neutrality, and there is a need for a focus closer to the everyday experience of citizens. Such a focus can be established by the topic of food and health. Last not least, it will be crucial to develop a pan-European debate about the topic of how to finance the EGD, a challenge that allows and requires to reflect about the scope and limitations of European solidarity.

Depending on the countries where each topic will be used as focus for participative events, particular items will be used in the analysis of the resulting data to link the topic with the particular conditions of specific countries. Regardless of topics and countries, however, cross-cutting issues will be made explicit. This holds in particular for gender equality and the many forms of discrimination not yet overcome in the EU. Finally, a key cross-cutting issue will be the reflection on how new formats of deliberation can foster the resonance needed for today's democratic institutions to successfully tackle the challenges of the future.

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7. Annex

Non-public Online Workshop Dialogue on selected European Green Deal Policy Priorities 12 January 2023, 9:30 – 13:00

Background

Projects financed under the Green Deal Calls (GDC), in total 73, are supported by the Green Deal Projects Support Office (GD-SO) with an aim of enhancing synergies, ensuring collaboration and sharing of project results. The projects have been grouped in five working groups (WGs), to explore potential similarities and shared interests. By the time of the first non-public online workshop, WGs will have met two times.

During these meetings, project coordinators expressed the need for more detailed information about the Commission policy priorities in their respective areas (climate change, biodiversity, clean energy, food, health, and urban environment and mobility).

All WGs aim at sharing project results with relevant policy units at the Commission. One of the objectives of the GD-SO is to identify synergies among projects and provide synthesized information to the relevant DGs, with the support of DG RTD.

Objective

The main objective of the workshop is to provide detailed information about the **Commission policy priorities related to the implementation of the selected European Green Deal policies** and to outline the ways in which projects supported by the GD-SO can contribute to the implementation of these policies.

Further aim is to enable project coordinators to have an open discussion with the policy officers and to gain a better understanding of the possible ways their **project results can feed into the Commission policy processes**, particularly those that are planned for the coming years when projects financed under the Green Deal Call will start having tangible results. In the same way, the event will give policy officers the possibility to directly interact with the projects during the open discussion and ask questions.

Target audience and format

This is a closed event; the workshop is primarily targeted at GDC project coordinators and relevant DGs that are interested in the GDC project results.

The list of policy areas that will be discussed is included in the agenda below. The aim is to allow project coordinators to choose the theme they find most relevant for their project. In case the project is contributing to more than one theme, two or three people representing the project can join the workshop to allow participation in relevant parallel sessions.

GD-SO will ensure the necessary follow-up and sharing of information.

Speakers

- Representatives of the European Commission working on the selected policy areas
- Representatives of the GDC projects

Tentative Agenda

Time	Agenda item
09:30 - 09:40	Meeting etiquette, TBC (moderator)
09:40 – 09:45	Welcome message, Emilie Vandam, DG RTD
09:45 – 10:00	European Green Deal policy priorities for the year ahead, TBC (general overview for all participants)
10:00 – 10:20	Citizen participation (Nora Allavoine, RTD.D4)
10:20 – 10:25	Short explanation on parallel sessions (structure, purpose)
10:25 – 11:25	<p>Parallel sessions – part 1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Short overview of the projects by the session facilitator: 10 mins - Presentation of the policy priorities and policy developments: 10 mins (European Commission) - Q&A and open discussion on the Commission’s expectations in terms of policy inputs from GDC projects: 40 mins <p>The breakout rooms will focus on the following areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Climate action: Irene Bonvissuto (CLIMA.E1) and Sophie Berger (RTD.B3) - Biodiversity: Caroline Pottier (ENV.A3) and Paola Lepori/Franz Immer (RTD.B3) - Clean, affordable and secure energy: Jens Bartholmes (ENER.B5) and Philippe Schild (RTD.C1) - Food: Ana Patricia Lopez Blanco (AGRI.F2) and Cindy Schoumacher (RTD.B2) - Health: Aleksandra Malyska (ENV.B2) and Egle Simelyte (RTD.D2) - Urban environment: Christos FRAGAKIS (RTC.C2) - Mobility: Dimitrios Vartis (MOVE.B3) and Agnieszka Zaplatka (RTD.C3)
11:25 – 11:40	Coffee break
11:40 – 12:30	<p>Parallel session – part 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Questions from policy officers to projects (sent to the projects in advance): answers from projects and open discussion
12:30 – 13:00	Plenary: Conclusions, closing remarks and future steps

This agenda is intended only for the recipients it has been directly shared with by the Green Deal Projects Support Office. To contact the support office, please email support@greendealprojects.eu